

1 **SLX1B is active during transformation and controls relapse and resistance in human cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We recently discovered SLX1B induction in a Brca1-deficient setting. To gain insight into processes
7 SLX1B participates in, we queried a collection of whole transcriptome datasets for SLX1B activation. A
8 dataset describing transcriptional activity in TNBC cells in vitro comparing cells with response or no
9 response to the chemotherapeutic agent irinotecan was retrieved. In vivo, SLX1B expression distinguished
10 partial versus complete response in patients treated with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer. Genetic
11 manipulation of a master homeobox factor also resulted in SLX1A/B perturbation.

12 The data supported a hypothesis arguing that genomic instability, and changes in expression of any
13 machinery that can generate such instability is a recurrent trigger that ultimately drives disease relapse in
14 cancer (recurrence) and treatment failure during treatment for cancer (partial response, residual disease
15 or complete response)

Results

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The data supported a hypothesis arguing that genomic instability, and changes in expression of any machinery that can generate such instability is a recurrent trigger that ultimately drives disease relapse in cancer (recurrence) and treatment failure during treatment for cancer (partial response or residual disease versus complete response).

Defective mismatch repair in irinotecan non-responsive cells.

Mismatch repair genes MSH2 and MSH6 were repressed in irinotecan non-responsive cells. Mismatch repair deficiency is an established driver of genomic instability. MLH1 was similarly depleted in non-responsive TNBC cells.

BRCA2 expression distinguishes treatment responsiveness in irinotecan-treated TNBC cells.

BRCA2, ERCC6L2 and the NHEJ/HR factor Xrcc5 (KU80) were each among the genes whose expression was most significantly silenced across the transcriptome in treatment non-responsive TNBC cells *in vitro*, as were MMR genes PMS1 and MMS22L.

Rad18, Rad23a, Rad23b and Rad51C silencing was observed together with activation of Rad50, Rad51B, Rad17 and Rad21L1.

Other changes we observed that we surmised might contribute to context-specific genomic instability in cancer cells treated with a chemotherapeutic agent included depletion of the polymerase Rev1, depletion of PARP1 with activation of PARP6 and PARP10, and expression of a translesion repair specific polymerase indicative of repair of a lesion process, Poli.

Finally, we found activation of 53bp1, a p53 target gene that serves important functions in and orchestrates subsequent events for DNA repair during genomic instability associated with requirement for HR/NHEJ.

SLX1A/B expression distinguishes partial from complete responses to trastuzumab in HER2+ breast cancer.

Importantly, in a small cohort of humans with HER2+ breast cancer whose total tumor transcriptomes were compared based on response or failure to the HER2-targeted therapy trastuzumab, SLX1B and SLX1A were leading gene products whose expression was depleted in the primary tumors in those who had failed treatment, or otherwise interpreted as possessing resistance disease (CR, complete responses versus RD, or residual disease) *in vivo*.

PAX8 depletion results in SLX1A/B perturbation.

Whole transcription data measuring total transcription in human cancer cells (a transformed cell line) *in vitro* following depletion of the master (hierarchically-central) homeobox factor PAX8 demonstrated that homeobox expression changes could result in significant depletion of SLX1A and SLX1B, supporting a mechanism by which a transcriptional circuit based in genomic instability involving an instability-inducing event (most often, an expression change) and activation of homeoboxes that permit re-entry to the fully transformed state (loss of response or disease recurrence). Accordingly, PAX8 depletion in human cells *in vitro* concomitantly resulted in depletion of mismatch repair enzymes MSH2 and MSH6.

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Discussion

We present here from an in vitro model using human triple negative breast cancer cells, a collection of transcriptional events curated from the total collection of changes in gene expression across the transcriptome associated with lack of response to a chemotherapeutic agent, irinotecan, evidence supporting a hypothesis that argued that genomic instability resulting from any number of a wide range of gene expression changes that can result in genomic instability are a direct and proximal cause of treatment failure or disease relapse (recurrence) in human cancer.

Future studies will evaluate the concept that such instability promotes both loss of treatment response during cancer therapy as well as relapse of disease in previously treated cancer patients by triggering sustained oncogene and homeobox expression resulting from instability, which likely requires an as of yet unidentified factor that supports what might be simplified as epigenetic reinforcement of homeobox and oncogene activation resulting from genomic instability.